

Polymetallic Complexes. Part-XLII. Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury(II) with a ONNO Donor Azo Dye, 4,4'-Bis(ethylcyanoacetate-2'-azo)diphenyl

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In continuation of our earlier work on the preparation and characterisation of polydentate azo dye ligands and their polymetallic complexes¹, the present report describes the synthesis of a bis-bidentate azo dye ligand having ONNO donor atoms and its dinuclear complexes with bivalent Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd and Hg.

Results and Discussion

Analysis and conductance data show the composition of the complexes as $[M_2LCl_4(H_2O)_4]$ and $[M'_2LCl_4]$, where $M(II) = Co, Cu$; $M'(II) = Ni, Zn, Cd, Hg$; $L = 4,4'$ -bis(ethylcyanoacetate-2'-azo)-diphenyl. The complexes (Table 1) are amorphous in nature having high melting points, and are insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in DMF. The complexes are found to be non-electrolytes with Λ_M values of 4.7–6.5 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

Ir spectrum of the ligand revealed three principal bands at 1 630 ($C=O$), 2 225 ($C\equiv N$) and 1 500 cm^{-1} ($N=N$). In the spectra of the complexes the $\nu_{C=O}$ and $\nu_{N=N}$ bands appeared at $\sim 1 595$ and $\sim 1 490 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, indicating the coordination of carbonyl oxygen of the esteric group² and one of the azo nitrogen³ of each group of the ligand to the metal ions. The $\nu_{C=N}$ band did not undergo any change in the metal complexes showing the non-coordination of cyano nitrogen atoms. The presence of coordinated water molecules in the Co^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes is in-

dicated by the appearance of broad band at $\sim 3 300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ followed by sharp peaks at 825–840 and ca 725–750 cm^{-1} assignable to OH stretching, rocking and wagging vibrations respectively⁴. The conclusive evidence of bonding of the ligand to the metal ions is indicated by the appearance of bands at 490–500 ($M-O$) and 430–450 cm^{-1} ($M-N$)⁵. The Ni complex is diamagnetic and the sub-normal magnetic moments of the Co (2.9 B.M.) and Cu (1.5 B.M.) complexes indicate metal-metal interaction thereby supporting a dinuclear structure⁶.

TABLE 1- ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd / (Colour)	Analysis% (Found/Calcd.)		
	M	N	Cl
L (Brown)	-	18.8 (19.44)	-
$[Co_2LCl_4(H_2O)_4]$ (Dark brown)	14.70 (15.22)	10.20 10.85	17.80 18.32
$[Ni_2LCl_4]$ (Red)	16.50 (16.98)	11.70 12.15	20.10 20.51
$[Cu_2LCl_4(H_2O)_4]$ (Light brown)	16.10 (16.43)	10.20 10.86	17.70 18.34
$[Zn_2LCl_4]$ (Reddish yellow)	18.20 (18.55)	11.30 11.92	19.50 20.12
$[Cd_2LCl_4]$ (Grey)	27.80 (28.47)	10.10 10.51	17.20 17.75
$[Hg_2LCl_4]$ (Grey)	40.60 (41.14)	8.20 8.61	14.10 14.54

The electronic spectrum of the Co^{II} complex showed ligand field bands at 8 950, 18 075, 21 170 and 35 340 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F)$ \rightarrow ${}^4T_{2g}(F)$, \rightarrow ${}^4A_{2g}(F)$, \rightarrow ${}^4T_{1g}(P)$ and C.T.

transitions respectively. The ligand field parameters like Dq (912.5 cm^{-1}), B (826.3 cm^{-1}), β_{35} (0.851), ν_2/ν_1 (2.02) and σ (17.5) are suggestive of an octahedral environment around the metal ions⁷. The Ni^{II} complex exhibited two bands at 16370 and 17450 cm^{-1} attributable to the transitions $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_g$ respectively, in support of a square-planar stereochemistry around the metal ion⁸. The Cu^{II} complex showed a broad asymmetric band at $13470\text{--}15250 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $^2E_g \rightarrow ^2T_{2g}$ transition in a distorted octahedral geometry⁹.

The ^1H nmr spectrum of the ligand displayed a complex pattern at δ 6.70–8.30, a triplet at 2.96 and a quartet at 2.05 attributable to eight phenyl protons, six methyl protons and four methylene protons respectively. Therefore nmr data present two ethyl groups in the ligand.

The esr spectrum of the copper complex recorded at X-band showed¹⁰ g_{av} value to be 2.14. This type of spectrum may result either due to dynamic or pseudo-rotational type of Jahn-Teller distortion or due to extensive exchange coupling operating between the $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{--Cu}^{\text{II}}$ ions in a dinuclear structures¹¹.

The Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are found to be tetrahedral based upon analytical and ir spectral data.

Hence, considering the bis-bidentate nature of the ligand, dinuclear structure can be tentatively suggested for the complexes (Fig. 1).

when $M = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ and Cu^{II} , $X = \text{H}_2\text{O}$
when $M = \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} , $X = \text{Nil}$

Fig. 1

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R grade. The

ligand was prepared by the usual method for preparing of an azo dye. The metal complexes were prepared by adding the ethanolic solution of metal chlorides to the ligand solution in dioxane in 2 : 1 molar ratio and refluxing the reaction mixture for 3 h over a heating mantle at $110\text{--}20^\circ$. On cooling, solid metal complexes that separated out were washed with ethanol, ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Metal, nitrogen and chloride contents were determined by standard methods. Conductance was measured in 10^{-3} M dimethyl formamide. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy method at room temperature. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (10^{-2} M DMF) on a Hilger and Watt UVispeck spectrophotometer, esr spectra on a E-4 spectrometer and nmr spectra on a EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer.

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